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AI meets toxicology

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Computational toxicology uses *in silico* tools to support integrative approaches for toxicological research and chemical safety assessments via predictive modeling. Traditional approaches are frequently based on quantitative structure-activity relationship studies, which use representations of chemical structures as molecular descriptors, or read across approaches, which exploit the structural similarity of molecules. Modern efforts are devoted to the development of robust interpretable models that have mechanistic interpretations within, e.g. Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOPs), which are combined with *in vitro* measurements to predict *in vivo* responses. The difficulties arise from the limited amount and heterogeneity of data, as well as the complexity of interpolation of *in vivo* endpoints based on *in silico* and *in vitro* data.

Modern Machine Learning based on deep neural networks (DNNs), which form the basis of Artificial Intelligence (AI), is gaining popularity in the field of computational toxicology. These methods can digest large amounts of information and provide reliable predictions for new molecules. Notably, such methods need not rely on descriptors, but can learn their internal representations based on text or molecular graphs. They can also incorporate non-traditional information, such as images produced by high content screening, to better utilize results of *in vitro* measurements. Emerging solutions include the use of meta- and transfer-learning approaches, which enable the pre-training of models on a large corpus of chemical data of different modalities, and then efficiently applies the models to small datasets using few-shot and zero-shot learning approaches, providing potential alternatives to read-across methods. The estimation of the accuracy of such predictions, which allows for the discrimination between reliable vs non-reliable predictions, is another important direction of the development of these methods. Being considered for a long time as black boxes, DNNs can become interpretable via eXplainable AI (XAI) methods. All the developments open new perspectives for the use of AI in toxicology.

In my presentation, I will recapitulate the recent developments in AI methods, and discuss their impact on computational toxicology as showcased in the studies performed within the Advanced Machine Learning for Innovative Drug Discovery (AIDD) project, as well as studies in the respective special issue published by ChemResTox.

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